

1 **Test-retest reliability of the Manikin Task and the robotic Kinarm Approach-Avoidance**
2 **Task as measures of approach and avoidance tendencies towards physical activity and**
3 **sedentary behaviours: A registered report**
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13 **ABSTRACT**

14 **Background.** Assessing approach-avoidance tendencies towards physical activity and
15 sedentary behaviours requires tasks that produce stable measurements over time. However,
16 neither the most used task to assess these tendencies, the Manikin Task, nor a newly developed
17 robotic task, the Kinarm Approach-Avoidance Task, have yet been evaluated for test-retest
18 reliability.

19 **Objective.** To assess the test-retest reliability of the Manikin Task and the Kinarm Approach-
20 Avoidance Task.

21 **Methods.** Healthy adults will perform the approach-avoidance tasks during two sessions
22 separated by one day. Approach-avoidance tendencies will be assessed using bias scores
23 derived from reaction times, time to peak velocity, x-flips, and opposite displacement. Bias
24 scores will be computed using both linear mixed-effects models and median-based methods.
25 Test-retest reliability will be quantified using two-way mixed-effects, single-measure intraclass
26 correlation coefficients for relative consistency and absolute agreement. Internal consistency
27 will be estimated using repeated split-half procedures and two-way random-effects, single-
28 measure, intraclass correlation coefficients for absolute-agreement. Standard error of
29 measurement, minimal detectable change, and systematic session effects will be computed to
30 quantify measurement precision and systematic bias.
31

32 **Keywords.** Psychology, Motivation, Robotics, Psychometrics, Exercise, Sedentary Behaviour
33

INTRODUCTION

Dual-process models of physical activity posit that physical activity behaviours need to be considered from the perspective of both controlled attitudes (e.g., intentions) and automatic attitudes (e.g., approach-avoidance tendencies).¹⁻³ Automatic attitudes, also called implicit attitudes, are defined as traces of cumulative past experiences that mediate favourable or unfavourable feeling, thought, or action towards a social object.⁴ They are activated by environmental and contextual cues through learned associations, operate mostly outside of conscious awareness,^{1,5} contribute to the regulation of physical activity,⁶ and can predict spontaneous physical activity behaviours.⁷

Automatic attitudes can be classified into three categories: cognitive, affective, and motivational.^{8,9} One of the most studied processes of motivational automatic attitudes is approach-avoidance tendencies, defined as the automatic impulse to move towards or away from stimuli.¹⁰ While some automatic processes are more evaluative (e.g., affective evaluation), approach-avoidance tendencies are more action-oriented processes and are considered to be more closely related to behaviour.^{1,3}

In physical activity research, these tendencies have been primarily studied using the Manikin Task, a keyboard-based task in which reaction times are measured by moving an on-screen manikin towards (i.e., approach) or away from (i.e., avoid) stimuli depicting physical activity and sedentary behaviours.¹⁰ Recently, a new robotic approach-avoidance task was developed on the Kinarm endpoint platform.¹¹ Referred to as the Kinarm Approach-Avoidance Task (KAAT), this task enables a bimanual, multidirectional, and dynamic assessment of spatiotemporal components of approach-avoidance tendencies through the coordinated manipulation of two handles in a virtual environment. A registered report is currently underway to evaluate the convergent, concurrent, and predictive validity of the KAAT.¹² However, its reliability has not yet been examined.

Test-retest reliability refers to the consistency, reproducibility, and agreement between repeated measurements obtained from the same individuals using the same tool under the same conditions.¹³ It can be assessed using intraclass correlation coefficients (ICCs), which quantify two complementary forms of reliability: consistency and agreement. Consistency (or relative reliability or rank-order stability)¹⁴ reflects the extent to which individuals maintain the same relative position within a group across raters or over time, even when systematic differences in scores are present. This form of reliability accounts for random measurement error (e.g., momentary inattention), but not systematic measurement error (e.g., learning, familiarisation effects). Agreement (or absolute reliability) refers to the extent to which repeated measurements yield similar raw scores for the same individual across raters or time points.¹⁵ Unlike consistency, agreement accounts for both random error and systematic sources of measurement error, such that systematic shifts in scores reduce reliability estimates.

A systematic review reported that only four studies in the approach-avoidance literature have examined test-retest reliability¹⁶, and these were conducted in food¹⁷, alcohol addiction^{18,19}, and fear-related paradigms.²⁰ Test-retest reliability was poor, ranging from .01 to .35.¹⁶ In physical activity research, neither traditional (e.g., Manikin Task) nor newly developed approach-avoidance tasks (e.g., KAAT) have been evaluated for test-retest reliability.

1 **Table 1.** A priori hypotheses categorized by reliability type for measures of approach-
 2 avoidance bias towards physical activity and sedentary behaviour.

Test-Retest Reliability of Reaction-Time-Based Approach-Avoidance Bias (H1)	
Physical Activity Stimuli	Sedentary Stimuli
<i>Consistency</i>	
H1a: ICC _{Content-Based KAAT} > ICC _{Manikin Task}	H1b: ICC _{Content-Based KAAT} > ICC _{Manikin Task}
H1c: ICC _{Frame-Based KAAT} > ICC _{Manikin Task}	H1d: ICC _{Frame-Based KAAT} > ICC _{Manikin Task}
H1e: ICC _{Content-Based KAAT} > ICC _{Frame-Based KAAT}	H1f: ICC _{Content-Based KAAT} > ICC _{Frame-Based KAAT}
<i>Absolute Agreement</i>	
H1g: ICC _{Content-Based KAAT} > ICC _{Manikin Task}	H1h: ICC _{Content-Based KAAT} > ICC _{Manikin Task}
H1i: ICC _{Frame-Based KAAT} > ICC _{Manikin Task}	H1j: ICC _{Frame-Based KAAT} > ICC _{Manikin Task}
H1k: ICC _{Content-Based KAAT} > ICC _{Frame-Based KAAT}	H1l: ICC _{Content-Based KAAT} > ICC _{Frame-Based KAAT}
Test-Retest Reliability of Kinematic-Based Approach-Avoidance Bias (H2)	
Physical Activity Stimuli	Sedentary Stimuli
<i>Consistency</i>	
H2a: ICC _{Time to Peak Velocity} ≥ .50	H2d: ICC _{Time to Peak Velocity} ≥ .50
H2b: ICC _{Opposite Displacement} ≥ .50	H2e: ICC _{Opposite Displacement} ≥ .50
H2c: ICC _{X-Flips} ≥ .50	H2f: ICC _{X-Flips} ≥ .50
<i>Absolute Agreement</i>	
H2g: ICC _{Time to Peak Velocity} ≥ .50	H2j: ICC _{Time to Peak Velocity} ≥ .50
H2h: ICC _{Opposite Displacement} ≥ .50	H2k: ICC _{Opposite Displacement} ≥ .50
H2i: ICC _{X-Flips} ≥ .50	H2l: ICC _{X-Flips} ≥ .50
Score Reliability (H3)	
Physical Activity Score	Sedentary Score
<i>Manikin Task</i>	
H3a: ICC _{Mixed-Effects Models} > ICC _{Median Difference}	H3b: ICC _{Mixed-Effects Models} > ICC _{Median Difference}
<i>Content-Based KAAT</i>	
H3c: ICC _{Mixed-Effects Models} > ICC _{Median Difference}	H3d: ICC _{Mixed-Effects Models} > ICC _{Median Difference}
<i>Frame-Based KAAT</i>	
H3e: ICC _{Mixed-Effects Models} > ICC _{Median Difference}	H3f: ICC _{Mixed-Effects Models} > ICC _{Median Difference}
Internal Consistency Within Each Session (H4)	
Physical Activity Stimuli	Sedentary Stimuli
H4a: Split-Half ICC _{Content-Based KAAT} > Split-Half ICC _{Manikin Task}	H4b: Split-Half ICC _{Content-Based KAAT} > Split-Half ICC _{Manikin Task}
H4c: Split-Half ICC _{Frame-Based KAAT} > Split-Half ICC _{Manikin Task}	H4d: Split-Half ICC _{Frame-Based KAAT} > Split-Half ICC _{Manikin Task}

3 Notes. H = hypothesis, ICC = Intraclass Correlation Coefficient, KAAT = Kinarm Approach-Avoidance Task. ICC ≥ .50 interpreted as moderate
 4 reliability.²¹

5 The objective of this study is to assess the test-retest reliability of three approach-
 6 avoidance tasks: the Manikin Task, the content-based KAAT, and the frame-based KAAT.

7 Our primary hypothesis (**H1**) is that the KAAT variants will demonstrate higher test-
 8 retest reliability than the Manikin Task. Although the multidirectional nature of the KAAT may
 9 introduce additional movement variability, the task captures continuous movement dynamics
 10 rather than relying solely on discrete reaction-time responses. By integrating richer kinematic
 11 information across the movement trajectory, the KAAT may provide a more stable estimate of
 12 approach-avoidance tendencies across sessions. In addition, we hypothesized that the content-
 13 based KAAT will demonstrate higher test-retest reliability than the frame-based KAAT.
 14 Because participants respond directly to stimulus content in the content-based variant,
 15 responses may be more consistent than in the frame-based variant, in which responses are based
 16 solely on the surrounding geometric shape rather than the stimulus content itself. Compared
 17 with semantic categories, such as physical activity and sedentary behaviour, geometric shapes

1 may provide less salient and less distinctive response cues, potentially increasing trial-level
2 variability. Our second hypothesis (**H2**) is that the approach-avoidance bias derived from
3 kinematic variables will demonstrate at least moderate test-retest reliability ($ICC \geq .50$). Our
4 third hypothesis (**H3**) is that scores derived from linear mixed-effects models will show higher
5 reliability than traditional median-based bias scores across tasks, owing to their improved
6 handling of trial-level variability. Our fourth hypothesis (**H4**) is that internal consistency within
7 each session will be greater for the KAAT variants compared with the Manikin Task (Table 1).
8

9 **METHODS**

10 **Participants**

11 Participants are recruited via emails, posters, and word of mouth. Inclusion criteria are
12 being between 18 and 60 years of age and the ability to communicate fluently in French or
13 English. Exclusion criteria include any conditions that could influence the results, such as self-
14 reported depression, upper limb injuries, a history of psychiatric or neurological disorders,
15 alcohol or drug abuse, or the use of psychotropic medications or illicit substances that may
16 affect attention or neurological functioning. The study was approved by the University of
17 Ottawa Research Ethics Board (H-01-25-11075). All participants provide informed consent and
18 are not compensated for their participation. Data collection began in May 2026 and will
19 continue until May 2027, or until the target sample size is reached, whichever occurs first.
20 Although some data have been collected, no observations, preprocessing, or analyses have been
21 or will be conducted prior to Stage 1 In-Principle Acceptance (IPA), which corresponds to
22 Level 3 of bias control according to the Peer Community In Registered Report taxonomy.

23 **Sample Size Justification and Precision Analysis**

24 Test-retest reliability will be operationalized using two complementary forms of the
25 two-way mixed-effects, single-measurement $ICC_{(3,1)}$ estimates: consistency and absolute
26 agreement. Because the two sessions are predefined and represent fixed rather than randomly
27 sampled measurement sessions, a mixed-effects model was selected over the random-effects
28 $ICC_{(2,1)}$.²¹ The consistency estimate will serve as the primary index of reliability because it
29 assesses the stability of individual differences independently of potential systematic session
30 effects (e.g., learning or familiarisation). Absolute agreement will be reported to quantify the
31 reproducibility of observed scores across sessions. Sample size planning followed precision-
32 based recommendations for reliability studies. Specifically, we used the approach described by
33 Bonett (2002), whereby sample size is selected to achieve a target confidence interval width
34 for the ICC estimate.²²

35 A planning value of $ICC = .50$ was adopted because the reliability of the KAAT is
36 unknown and because .50 corresponds to the boundary between poor and moderate reliability
37 according to conventional guidelines.²¹ With $N = 100$ participants measured twice ($k = 2$),
38 corresponding to the maximum number of participants who can feasibly be recruited and tested,
39 the Bonett approximation indicates that the expected width of the 95% confidence interval is
40 approximately $w = 0.295$ (half-width $\approx \pm 0.148$).²² This level of precision represents a
41 compromise between statistical accuracy and feasibility in behavioural reliability research.
42 Moreover, this sample size is consistent with COSMIN methodological quality standards for

1 reliability studies, which classify samples of $N \geq 100$ as providing very good methodological
2 quality for the evaluation of measurement properties.²³

4 Study Procedure

5 Two sessions are conducted at approximately the same time of day. During the first
6 session, participants perform the Manikin Task, the content-based KAAT and the frame-based
7 KAAT, with a five-minute rest period between tasks. After completing the three approach-
8 avoidance tasks, participants complete questionnaires assessing age, sex, gender, weight,
9 height, and physical activity during the previous 24 h. The retest session is conducted one day
10 after the initial assessment (Figure 1). This interval is intended to provide a sufficiently long
11 delay to minimize short-term memory effects and task familiarisation while remaining short
12 enough to reduce the likelihood of genuine changes in automatic approach-avoidance
13 tendencies. Previous research on implicit measures in physical activity contexts has shown that
14 these processes can change within one week.²⁴ Because recent physical activity can influence
15 participants' affective, cognitive, and behavioural state at the time of assessment²⁵, participants
16 are instructed to refrain from exercise during the 24 h preceding each session to minimize
17 potential state-related variability.

18 Task order is held constant across the test and retest sessions for each participant but
19 counterbalanced across participants using the six possible task orders. This approach avoids
20 introducing additional within-person variance by preserving comparable measurement
21 conditions, and facilitates comparison between tasks while accounting for potential order
22 effects (e.g., inattention, fatigue).²⁶

24 **Figure 1.** Study timeline. KAAT = Kinarm Approach-Avoidance Task. Task order
25 is counterbalanced across participants but held constant between the test and retest
26 sessions for each participant.
27

28 Approach-Avoidance Tasks

29 This study includes three tasks designed to assess the same construct, approach-
30 avoidance tendencies: two KAAT variants and one computer-based task, the Manikin Task.
31 Demonstration videos of the three tasks are available on the project's GitHub repository.²⁷

33 Content-Based Robotic KAAT

34 The Kinarm Endpoint robotic system (Kinarm, Canada) is equipped with a 2-
35 dimensional augmented reality display and provides high-resolution kinematic data. In the
36 KAAT, participants stand while holding the robot's handles, with each hand represented on the
37 display by a white cursor (Figure 2A). In the content-based variant, the task begins with on-
38 screen instructions illustrating the upcoming condition. To initiate each block of trials,
39 participants use either hand to place the white cursor into a green circle located at the centre of

1 the workspace. For each trial, a blue circle then appears on either the left or right side of the
 2 display with equal probability. Once the participant places the white cursor of the appropriate
 3 hand (i.e., blue circle on the left requires the left-hand cursor) into the blue circle and holds it
 4 there for 500 to 750 ms, a stimulus target depicting a pictogram appears at one of twelve
 5 possible locations positioned 10 cm from the start target and separated by 30-degree increments
 6 (Figure 2B). Simultaneously, a second target consisting of an empty white circle appears at the
 7 opposite location. Participants are asked to react to the pictogram itself by moving the white
 8 cursor towards or away from the pictogram. If neither target is reached within 3000 ms, a “Too
 9 Slow!” message is displayed for 750 ms and the trial ends. If the participant incorrectly
 10 approaches or avoids a target, an “Incorrect!” text is displayed for 750 ms before the trial ends
 11 (Figure 2C).¹¹

12

13

14 **Figure 2. Content-Based Robotic Kinarm Approach-Avoidance Task.** (A)
 15 Experimental setup. (B) Example trial in which a neutral stimulus appears at the
 16 west position and the open circle appears at the opposite location. Dashed circles
 17 illustrate the possible stimulus locations for visualisation purposes only and are not
 18 visible to participants during the task. (C) Example trial in which the participant is
 19 instructed to approach sedentary stimuli and avoid physical activity stimuli. The
 20 hands are shown for illustrative purposes only and are not visible to participants
 21 during the actual task.

22

23 *Frame-Based KAAT*

24 In the frame-based variant of the KAAT, participants are instructed to react to the
 25 geometric shape (i.e., a circle or a square) surrounding the pictogram. For example, they may
 26 be instructed to move the white cursor towards the pictograms surrounded by a circle and away
 27 from pictograms surrounded by a square (Figure 4). This variant is thought to rely less on
 28 explicit processing of stimulus content because participants are not instructed to intentionally
 29 attend to the physical-activity or sedentary meaning of the pictograms.¹⁶ To avoid confusion

1 with the shapes of interest, the empty white circle at the opposite location that serves as the
2 avoidance target is replaced by a hexagon in this variant of the KAAT.

3 4 *Manikin Task*

5 The manikin task is implemented in Inquisit 6 software.^{28–30} Participants perform the
6 task in a standing position with the laptop in front of them, with their index fingers positioned
7 on the “U” and “N” keys (Figure 3A). Pressing the “U” key moves the avatar upward, whereas
8 pressing the “N” key moves the avatar downward. When the avatar appears below the stimulus,
9 the “U” key is associated with an approach movement, and the “N” key is associated with an
10 avoidance movement. The opposite mapping applies when the avatar appears above the
11 stimulus.

12 The manikin task begins with on-screen textual instructions indicating the upcoming
13 condition. Each trial then starts with a fixation cross presented at the centre of the screen for a
14 random time ranging from 500 to 750 ms (Figure 3B). An avatar subsequently appears at either
15 the top or the bottom of the screen. After 1,000 ms, a stimulus is presented at the centre of the
16 screen. Pressing the correct key triggers the manikin movement and the onset of the next trial.
17 If a participant presses the incorrect key (e.g., pressing “U” when “N” is required), an
18 “ERROR” message is displayed for 800 ms and the trial ends. If no key is pressed within 7 s,
19 a “TOO SLOW” message is displayed for 800 ms before the trial ends.

21
22
23 **Figure 3. Manikin Task.** (A) Experimental setup for the manikin task. (B)
24 Example sequence in which the participant is instructed to approach physical
25 activity stimuli.

26 27 *Experimental and Neutral Conditions*

28 In the three approach-avoidance tasks, performance is assessed in two experimental
29 conditions (physical activity vs. sedentary stimuli) and two neutral conditions (ovals vs.
30 rectangles) (Figure 4). Neutral trials are used in the analyses as a baseline correction to control
31 for generic approach-avoidance tendencies.²⁹ One neutral block is administered at the
32 beginning of the task and the other at the end, with the two experimental blocks between them.
33 Approach-avoidance response mappings are counterbalanced across participants separately

1 for neutral and experimental blocks. Within each block, pictogram presentation order is
 2 randomized across both stimulus categories. Each block includes 48 trials, resulting in a total
 3 of 192 trials per task.

4 For the content-based KAAT and the Manikin Task, participants are instructed in one
 5 experimental condition to approach pictograms depicting physical activity and to avoid
 6 pictograms depicting sedentary behaviour. In the other experimental condition, the mapping
 7 is reversed, such that participants avoid physical activity stimuli and approach sedentary
 8 stimuli. In the neutral conditions, the experimental pictograms are replaced by geometric
 9 shapes (ovals or rectangles) matched to three physical activity pictograms (swimming, hiking,
 10 cycling) and three sedentary pictograms (couch, hammock, reading) in visual complexity and
 11 size.^{11,28-30} In one neutral condition, participants are instructed to approach pictograms
 12 depicting ovals and avoid pictograms depicting rectangles. In the other condition, the mapping
 13 is reversed.

14 For the frame-based KAAT, participants are instructed to approach or avoid the
 15 geometric shapes surrounding the pictograms. Within each condition, each pictogram appears
 16 equally often in approach- and avoidance-associated shape formats, thereby preventing
 17 systematic associations between stimulus content and movement direction.
 18

19
 20 **Figure 4.** Timeline and stimuli used in the three approach-avoidance tasks.
 21 Approach-avoidance mappings are counterbalanced across participants separately
 22 for neutral blocks (ovals vs. rectangles stimuli) and experimental blocks (physical
 23 activity vs. sedentary stimuli). Within each block, pictogram presentation order is
 24 randomized across both stimulus categories.

25
 26 *Reaction Times*

27 Incorrect responses, responses faster than 150 ms, and responses slower than 1500 ms
 28 will be excluded from the analyses. The lower threshold was selected as a trade-off between
 29 the retention of valid observations and the exclusion of anticipatory responses.³¹ The upper
 30 threshold was chosen based on prior work indicating this cut-off yields reliable estimates and
 31 maximizes sensitivity.³² Familiarisation trials (i.e., the first 15 trials of the study and the first 3
 32 trials of each subsequent condition) will be removed from the analyses.²⁸

33 For the manikin task, reaction time is defined as the interval between stimulus onset
 34 and the key press. For the content-based KAAT and the frame-based KAAT, reaction time is

1 defined as the interval between peripheral target onset and movement initiation. Movement
2 initiation is identified kinematically by first detecting the time point at which acceleration
3 exceeds 1,000 mm/s² and then tracing backward to the last time point at which acceleration
4 was above 200 mm/s². This procedure has been shown to provide a reliable and accurate
5 estimate of movement initiation based on kinematic data.³³

6 7 *Elapsed Time and Task Order*

8 Elapsed time is defined as the duration between task onset (manikin or content-based
9 KAAT or frame-based KAAT) and trial completion for each trial. Task order will also be
10 included as a categorical variable. These variables account for potential temporal and order-
11 related effects, including fatigue and learning.

12 13 *Kinematic Variables*

14 In addition to reaction time, three kinematic outcomes will be computed in the content-
15 based KAAT and frame-based KAAT to capture complementary aspects of movement
16 dynamics: a derivative measure, a complexity measure, and a measure of deviation (Figure 5).
17 These variables are thought to represent approach-avoidance conflicts³⁴, as altered movement
18 dynamics suggest that competing approach and avoidance tendencies were concurrently
19 activated, resulting in a conflict between task instructions and underlying tendencies during
20 movement execution.

21 The derivative measure, time to peak velocity, reflects reluctance to commit to action,
22 and is defined as the time elapsed from movement onset to the time point of maximum
23 movement velocity.^{35,36} Movement onset is defined using the same algorithm as described
24 above for reaction time determination. Time to peak velocity will be computed as the mean
25 time to peak velocity across correct trials, with longer times to peak velocity indicating delayed
26 motor commitment.

27 The complexity measure, x-flips, reflects wavering during movement execution and is
28 defined as the number of directional changes along the axis connecting the two response
29 targets^{36,37}, which will be computed as the number of sign changes in velocity leading to a
30 displacement greater than 1 mm. This variable will be computed as the mean number of x-flips
31 across correct trials, with a higher number of x-flips indicating greater decision difficulty.³⁸

32 The deviation measure, opposite displacement, reflects response competition by
33 capturing the extent to which the movement initially unfolds in the incorrect direction, and is
34 defined as the mean displacement in the direction opposite to the correct response, calculated
35 on correct trials. This variable is computed as the mean opposite displacement across correct
36 trials, with greater opposite displacement indicating greater response competition.

37

38

1 **Figure 5. Kinematic Variables.** (A) Example trial from the Kinarm Approach-
 2 Avoidance Task. Panels B-D provide schematic representations of the kinematic
 3 variables extracted from movement trajectories: (B) time to peak velocity, (C)
 4 number of x-flips, and (D) opposite displacement.

6 Computation of Approach-Avoidance Bias Scores

7 Bias Scores Based on Linear Mixed-Effects Models

8 Linear mixed-effects models will be fitted in R³⁹ using the *lme*⁴⁰ and *lmerTest*⁴¹
 9 packages. To ensure that reliability estimates correspond to the raw task-derived measures⁴²,
 10 the primary analysis will assess the reliability of the unadjusted approach-avoidance bias scores
 11 (i.e., models without covariates), consistent with previous reliability work on approach-
 12 avoidance tasks.¹⁶ For conciseness, the following model specification (Equation 1) is presented
 13 for reaction time only but will be estimated separately for each kinematic variable:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Reaction Time} \sim & \text{Movement} * \text{Stimulus Type} * \text{Session} \\
 & + (\text{Movement} * \text{Stimulus Type} | \text{Subject: Session}) \\
 & + (1 | \text{Pictogram})
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{1}$$

14
 15
 16
 17
 18
 19 Session number (1 or 2) will be represented by the variable *Session*. *Movement*
 20 (approach and avoid) will be deviation-coded (−0.5 and +0.5, respectively) so that the
 21 *Movement* coefficient represents the Avoid − Approach contrast. *Stimulus Type* (neutral,
 22 physical activity and sedentary behaviour) will be entered as a three-level categorical predictor
 23 using treatment coding, with neutral stimuli as the reference category. Planned contrasts will
 24 therefore compare physical activity and sedentary behaviour stimuli separately against neutral
 25 stimuli.

26 Random effects will include intercepts for *Pictogram* to account for stimulus-specific
 27 variability. To obtain session-specific bias estimates within a single model, random effects will
 28 also be specified for participants nested within sessions (*Subject:Session*).¹⁶ Specifically,
 29 random slopes for the *Movement* × *Stimulus Type* interaction will be included at the

1 Subject:Session level, allowing individual differences in approach-avoidance tendencies to
 2 vary across sessions. In cases of non-convergence or singular fit, the structure of the model will
 3 be simplified to balance model complexity, numerical stability, and statistical power.⁴³

4 Models will be estimated using restricted maximum likelihood (REML). Statistical
 5 assumptions will be evaluated using residual diagnostics (Q-Q plots and residual-versus-fitted
 6 plots). If substantial deviations from normality or homoscedasticity are observed, sensitivity
 7 analyses using log-transformed reaction times will be conducted to assess the robustness of the
 8 findings.

9 Neutral-adjusted approach-avoidance bias will be estimated separately for physical
 10 activity and sedentary behaviour using planned interaction contrasts. Specifically, for each
 11 experimental stimulus category, the contrast between avoidance and approach responses will
 12 be compared with the corresponding contrast for neutral stimuli (Equation 2):

$$\begin{aligned} \beta_{\text{Experimental Bias}} &= \\ &= (E[RT_{\text{Avoid Experimental}}] - E[RT_{\text{Approach Experimental}}]) \\ &- (E[RT_{\text{Avoid Neutral}}] - E[RT_{\text{Approach Neutral}}]) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

17 where $E[RT]$ denotes the reaction time estimated by the model, and experimental represents
 18 physical activity or sedentary stimuli. Thus, β is the model-based estimate of the same contrast
 19 captured by the traditional double-difference score computed from aggregated median reaction
 20 times, thereby accounting for individual generic approach-avoidance tendencies.

21 Session-specific estimates will be derived from participant-specific and session-specific
 22 empirical Bayes estimates. Scores will be based on the planned Stimulus Type \times Movement
 23 interaction contrasts, combining the relevant session-specific fixed effect terms with the
 24 corresponding Subject:Session random effects contributing to this contrast. The same
 25 computation will be applied to approach-avoidance bias derived from kinematic variables.

28 *Bias Scores Based on Medians*

29 The approach-avoidance bias towards physical activity and sedentary behaviour will be
 30 estimated directly at the participant level as a double-difference score, by subtracting the
 31 median reaction-time difference between avoidance and approach responses for neutral stimuli
 32 from the corresponding median reaction-time difference for experimental stimuli, as illustrated
 33 in Equation 3:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Experimental Bias} &= \\ &= (\text{median } RT_{\text{Avoid Experimental}} - \text{median } RT_{\text{Approach Experimental}}) \\ &- (\text{median } RT_{\text{Avoid Neutral}} - \text{median } RT_{\text{Approach Neutral}}) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

38 For reaction-time scores, positive values will indicate faster approach than avoidance
 39 responses towards experimental stimuli, reflecting a tendency to approach rather than avoid.
 40 For kinematic scores, positive values will indicate greater movement conflict during avoidance
 41 than approach trials, which will reflect a tendency to approach.

1 **Questionnaires**

2 *Demographic and Anthropometric Variables*

3 Sex (male, female), age (years), height (cm), weight (kg), and handedness will be self-
4 reported.

5

6 *Physical Activity During the Previous 24 Hours*

7 Physical activity during the previous 24 hours will be assessed using a modified version
8 of the International Physical Activity Questionnaire – Short Form (IPAQ–SF). This self-
9 administered questionnaire measures the duration of walking, moderate physical activity,
10 vigorous physical activity, and sedentary behaviour during the previous 24 hours.⁴⁴ Consistent
11 with the original scoring guidelines⁴⁵, time spent in each category will be weighted by a
12 metabolic equivalent of task (MET): 3.3 METs for walking, 4.0 METs for moderate physical
13 activity, and 8.0 METs for vigorous physical activity. Weighted activity scores will be summed
14 to obtain total physical activity, expressed in MET-min/day, representing overall daily physical
15 activity volume adjusted for intensity. Total physical activity will be included as a covariate in
16 sensitivity analyses to examine whether recent physical activity influences test-retest reliability
17 estimates.

18 **Descriptive Analyses**

19 Means and standard deviations will be reported for age, height, weight, and total
20 physical activity. Sex and handedness will be summarised using counts and percentages.
21 Descriptive statistics will be calculated separately for each session for reaction times, number
22 of errors, and kinematic variables, stratified by stimulus type and movement direction.

23

24 **Data Analysis**

25 *Test-Retest Reliability of Reaction-Time-Based Scores*

26 Consistency and agreement indices of test-retest reliability will be computed for each
27 task, stimulus type, and scoring method using the *irr* package in R.⁴⁶

28 Consistency, reflecting the stability of individual differences across sessions, will be
29 assessed using ICCs. Because the same participants will complete the same two testing sessions
30 (Time 1 and Time 2), and these sessions are not considered a random sample of possible testing
31 sessions, a two-way mixed-effects, single-measurement consistency ICC_(3,1) will be used as the
32 primary index of relative stability. This model is appropriate when the objective is to assess
33 whether individuals maintain their relative position within the sample across time. In addition,
34 a two-way mixed-effects, single-measurement absolute agreement ICC_(3,1) will be computed to
35 assess the extent to which individual scores remain numerically stable across sessions,
36 indicating absolute stability. Whereas the consistency-based ICC reflects stability in participant
37 ranking, the agreement-based ICC incorporates both random measurement error and potential
38 systematic shifts between sessions. Ninety-five percent confidence intervals (95% CI) will be
39 reported for all ICC estimates. Following conventional guidelines,²¹ ICC values < .50 will be
40 interpreted as poor, .50–.75 as moderate, .76–.90 as good, and >.90 as excellent reliability.

41 Differences between ICC estimates (H1, H3, and H4) will be quantified as $\Delta ICC = ICC_A$
42 $- ICC_B$. Uncertainty around these differences will be estimated using participant-level bootstrap
43 resampling with 1,000 iterations. At each bootstrap iteration, participants will be sampled with

1 replacement, and all observations associated with each task will be retained for each selected
2 participant. Scores and ICCs will then be recomputed, and the difference between the relevant
3 ICC estimates will be retained. The 2.5th and 97.5th percentiles of the bootstrap distribution
4 will be used as the 95% confidence interval for Δ ICC. A reliability difference will be considered
5 to support the corresponding directional hypothesis when the entire 95% bootstrap confidence
6 interval exceeds zero.

8 *Test-Retest Reliability of Kinematic-Based Scores*

9 For each participant and session, approach-avoidance bias derived from kinematic
10 outcomes will be computed using the procedure described above and will be used to compute
11 test-retest reliability indices. Consistency and absolute agreement will be assessed using two-
12 way mixed-effects, single-measurement ICC_(3,1) models. Reliability analyses will be conducted
13 separately for each task (content-based KAAT and frame-based KAAT), stimulus category
14 (physical activity and sedentary behaviour), and kinematic-based approach-avoidance bias
15 (time to peak velocity, x-flips, and opposite displacement).

17 *Internal Consistency*

18 Within-session reliability will be estimated using a resampling-based split-half
19 procedure. For each participant, session, and stimulus category (physical activity and sedentary
20 behaviour), trials will be randomly divided into two non-overlapping halves using stratified
21 sampling, ensuring that each half contains an equal number of observations from each
22 combination of Movement (approach vs. avoidance) and Stimulus Type (experimental vs.
23 neutral). For approach-avoidance bias scores, the linear mixed-effects model will be refitted
24 separately to each half using the model specification described above, yielding two independent
25 bias estimates per participant and session. To reduce dependency on any single arbitrary split
26 and obtain a more stable estimate of internal consistency, this procedure will be repeated 500
27 times using independent random stratified splits. For each iteration, agreement between the two
28 bias estimates will be quantified using a two-way random-effects absolute agreement ICC_(2,1).
29 Because split-half reliability reflects the reliability of a half-length measure, ICC values will be
30 adjusted using the Spearman-Brown correction to estimate the reliability of the full-length
31 task.^{47,48} For each task, stimulus category, scoring method, and session, the primary internal
32 consistency estimate will be the mean Spearman-Brown-corrected reliability ICC across the
33 500 splits. This approach assesses the extent to which trials within a session consistently capture
34 the same underlying construct.

35 For kinematic variables, the same split-half procedure will be applied. Within each half,
36 kinematic outcomes will be computed using the procedures described above before computing
37 ICC_(2,1) values and applying the Spearman-Brown correction. Split-half reliability values of .80
38 or higher will be interpreted as adequate for basic research.⁴⁹

39 For the comparison of internal consistency across tasks, reliability differences will be
40 quantified as Δ ICC using the same bootstrap procedure described for H1. At each bootstrap
41 iteration, participants will be sampled with replacement and all observations associated with
42 the selected participants will be retained. Within each bootstrap sample, the split-half procedure
43 will be repeated using 100 random stratified splits to reduce the influence of any single arbitrary
44 split while limiting computational burden. The mean Spearman-Brown-corrected ICC across

1 these 100 splits will be computed for each task, and the corresponding ΔICC value will be
2 retained. The 2.5th and 97.5th percentiles of the resulting bootstrap distribution will be used to
3 construct a 95% confidence interval for ΔICC . A reliability difference will be considered to
4 support the corresponding directional hypothesis when the entire 95% confidence interval
5 exceeds zero.

6 7 *Measurement Precision*

8 To quantify measurement precision at the individual level, the standard error of
9 measurement (SEM), which represents the expected variation in an individual's observed score
10 due to measurement error, will be computed using the absolute agreement ICC and the pooled
11 standard deviation: $SEM = SD_{pooled} \times \sqrt{1 - ICC}$

12 The minimal detectable change at the 95% confidence level (MDC_{95}), which represents
13 the smallest change that can be interpreted as exceeding measurement error with 95%
14 confidence, will then be calculated as: $MDC_{95} = 1.96 \times \sqrt{2} \times SEM$

15 These indices will complement ICC estimates by providing information about the
16 absolute precision of the measurements and the practical interpretability of individual-level
17 change.

18 19 *Systematic Session Effects*

20 To examine systematic session differences, approach-avoidance bias scores from
21 Session 1 and Session 2 will be compared separately for each task, stimulus category (physical
22 activity and sedentary behaviour), and scoring method using paired-sample t-tests. Mean
23 differences and their 95% confidence intervals will be reported, along with effect sizes
24 expressed as Cohen's d_z . To control family-wise error rate across multiple comparisons, p-
25 values will be adjusted using the Holm-Bonferroni procedure. Identification of systematic
26 session effects will help interpret discrepancies between consistency- and agreement-based ICC
27 estimates.

28 29 *Interpretation of the Test-Retest Results*

30 We will jointly interpret consistency- and agreement-based reliability indices with
31 systematic session effects. Specifically: (a) high consistency ICCs accompanied by lower
32 agreement ICCs and significant mean differences between sessions will be interpreted as
33 evidence of systematic session effects (e.g., learning or familiarisation) rather than instability
34 in individual differences; (b) low consistency and agreement ICCs will indicate poor
35 reproducibility arising from substantial within-person variability and/or measurement error; and
36 (c) high consistency and agreement ICCs accompanied by negligible mean differences will
37 support both rank-order stability and absolute score stability.

38 39 *Sensitivity Analysis*

40 To evaluate the robustness of the main analyses, sensitivity analyses will be conducted
41 by adding covariates to the linear mixed-effects models (Equation 4):

$$\begin{aligned}
& 1 \quad \text{Reaction Time} \sim \text{Movement} * \text{Stimulus Type} * \text{Session} + \text{Age} + \text{Sex} + \text{Height} \\
& 2 \quad \quad \quad * \text{Weight} + \text{Handedness} + \text{Elapsed Time} + \text{Task Order} \quad (4) \\
& 3 \quad \quad \quad + \text{Total Physical Activity} \\
& 4 \quad \quad \quad + (\text{Movement} * \text{Stimulus Type} | \text{Subject: Session}) + (1 | \text{Pictogram})
\end{aligned}$$

5 These analyses will assess whether the estimated approach-avoidance bias scores and
6 their associated reliability estimates remain robust after adjustment for participant
7 characteristics, recent physical activity, and order-related effects. Continuous covariates (age,
8 height, weight, elapsed time, and total physical activity) will be standardised using z-scores
9 prior to analysis to facilitate model convergence and interpretation.

11 **Data & Code Accessibility**

12 Data, R scripts, and materials used in this study will be made freely accessible in
13 Zenodo.²⁷

15 **Ethical Statement**

16 The study was approved by the University of Ottawa’s Research Ethics Board (H-01-
17 25-11075) and informed consent was collected in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki.

19 **Use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and AI-assisted technologies**

20 ChatGPT (OpenAI) and DeepL were used to refine the language, improve readability,
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31 **Competing Interests**

32 Matthieu P. Boisgontier is the founder, representative, and publication director of Peer
33 Community In Health & Movement Sciences (PCI HMS), and serves as a Recommender for
34 PCI Neuroscience and PCI Registered Reports. François Jabouille is a member of the Managing
35 Board of PCI HMS. Kayne Park is a Recommender for PCI HMS.

37 **Authors' Contributions**

38 Based on the Contributor Roles Taxonomy (CRediT)⁵⁰ individual author contributions
39 to this work will be as follows: François Jabouille: Conceptualization, Methodology,
40 Investigation, Data Curation, Formal Analysis, Visualisation, Writing – Original Draft, Writing
41 – Review and Editing, Supervision; Samantha Lee: Investigation; Kayne Park: Methodology,
42 Data Curation, Visualisation, Writing – Review and Editing; Matthieu Boisgontier:

1 Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal Analysis, Visualisation, Writing – Original Draft,
2 Writing – Review and Editing, Supervision, Project Administration, Funding Acquisition.

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27

TABLE

Table 2. Study design

Question	Hypotheses	Sampling plan	Analysis plan	Rationale for deciding the sensitivity of the test for confirming or disconfirming the hypothesis	Interpretation given different outcomes
<p>What is the test-retest reliability of reaction-time-based approach-avoidance bias scores across tasks?</p>	<p>H1: KAAT variants will demonstrate higher test-retest reliability than the Manikin Task</p>	<p>A planning value of ICC = .50 was adopted because the reliability of the KAAT is unknown and because .50 corresponds to the boundary between poor and moderate reliability according to conventional guidelines.²¹ With N = 100 participants measured twice (k = 2), corresponding to the maximum number of participants who can feasibly be recruited and tested, the Bonett approximation indicates that the expected width of the 95% confidence interval is approximately $w = 0.295$ (half-width $\approx \pm 0.148$).²² This level of precision represents a compromise between statistical accuracy and feasibility in behavioural reliability research. Moreover, this sample size is consistent with COSMIN methodological quality standards for reliability studies, which classify samples of $N \geq 100$ as providing very good methodological quality for the evaluation of measurement properties.²³</p>	<p>Consistency and agreement indices will be computed for each task, stimulus type, and scoring method using the <i>irr</i> package in R.⁴⁶ Because the same participants will complete the same two testing sessions (Time 1 and Time 2), and these sessions are not considered a random sample of possible testing sessions, consistency and absolute agreement ICCs will be computed using two-way mixed-effects, single-measurement consistency ICC_(3,1). 95% CI will be reported for all ICC estimates. Following conventional guidelines,²¹ ICC values < .50 will be interpreted as poor, .50–.75 as moderate, .76–.90 as good, and >.90 as excellent reliability. Differences between ICC estimates (H1, H3, and H4) will be quantified as $\Delta ICC = ICC_A - ICC_B$. Uncertainty around these differences will be estimated using participant-level bootstrap resampling with 1,000 iterations. At each bootstrap iteration, participants will be sampled with replacement, and all observations associated with each task will be retained for each selected participant. Scores and ICCs will then be recomputed, and the difference between the relevant ICC estimates will be retained. The 2.5th and 97.5th percentiles of the bootstrap distribution will be used as the 95% confidence interval for ΔICC.</p>	<p>Sensitivity will be determined primarily from the precision of the estimated reliability indices and reliability differences. For H1, H3, and H4, directional hypotheses will be considered supported when the 95% bootstrap confidence interval for the relevant ΔICC is entirely above zero. If the confidence interval includes zero, the hypothesis will not be considered supported.</p>	<p>Each ICC will be interpreted using conventional categories: < .50 = poor, .50–.75 = moderate, .76–.90 = good, > .90 = excellent.²¹ When confidence intervals span multiple categories, the compatible range of interpretations will be reported.</p> <p>For each type of ICC: H1 will be supported when the entire 95% bootstrap CI for ΔICC is above zero.</p> <p>If the 95% bootstrap CI includes zero, the comparison will be interpreted as inconclusive, even if point estimates are in the hypothesised direction.</p> <p>If the entire 95% bootstrap CI is below zero, this will be interpreted as evidence against the hypothesised reliability advantage of the corresponding task</p>
<p>What is the test-retest reliability of kinematic-based approach-avoidance bias scores?</p>	<p>H2: approach-avoidance bias derived from kinematic variables will demonstrate at least moderate test-retest reliability (ICC \geq .50).</p>		<p>Consistency and absolute agreement will be assessed using two-way mixed-effects, single-measurement ICC_(3,1) models. Reliability analyses will be conducted separately for each task (content-based KAAT and frame-based KAAT), stimulus category (physical activity and sedentary behaviour), and kinematic-based approach-avoidance bias (time to peak velocity, x-flips, and opposite displacement).</p>	<p>For H2, the hypothesis will be considered supported when ICC estimates for kinematic-based bias scores are at least moderate (ICC \geq .50), and 95% confidence intervals are above this threshold. Wide confidence intervals including values below .50 will be interpreted as insufficient support.</p>	<p>For each type of ICC: H2 will be supported for a given kinematic variable when the ICC confidence interval is \geq .50.</p> <p>If the confidence intervals include values below .50, H2 will be considered inconclusive, and reliability will be interpreted according to the range spanned by the confidence interval (e.g., poor-to-moderate).</p>

Question	Hypotheses	Sampling plan	Analysis plan	Rationale for deciding the sensitivity of the test for confirming or disconfirming the hypothesis	Interpretation given different outcomes
Do mixed-effects-model-derived scores show higher reliability than traditional median-bases bias scores?	H3: scores derived from linear mixed-effects models will show higher reliability than traditional median-based bias scores across tasks.		Same procedure as described for H1, with $\Delta ICC = ICC_{Mixed-effects model} - ICC_{Median difference}$.	Sensitivity will be determined primarily from the precision of the estimated reliability indices and reliability differences. For H1, H3, and H4, directional hypotheses will be considered supported when the 95% bootstrap confidence interval for the relevant ΔICC is entirely above zero. If the confidence interval includes zero, the hypothesis will not be considered supported.	<p>For each type of ICC: H3 will be supported when the entire 95% bootstrap CI for ΔICC is above zero.</p> <p>If the 95% bootstrap CI includes zero, results will be interpreted as inconclusive regarding a reliability difference between scoring methods.</p> <p>If the entire 95% bootstrap CI is below zero, this will indicate that the traditional median-based bias score is more reliable than the mixed-model-derived score for that task and stimulus category.</p>
What is the internal consistency of approach-avoidance bias scores within each session?	H4: internal consistency within each session will be greater for the KAAT variants compared with the Manikin Task.		Within-session reliability will be estimated using a resampling-based split-half procedure. For each participant, session, and stimulus category (physical activity and sedentary behaviour), trials will be randomly divided into two non-overlapping halves using stratified sampling, ensuring that each half contains an equal number of observations from each combination of Movement (approach vs. avoidance) and Stimulus Type (experimental vs. neutral). For approach-avoidance bias scores, the linear mixed-effects models will be refitted separately to each half, yielding two independent bias estimates per participant and session. To reduce dependency on any single arbitrary split and obtain a more stable estimate of internal consistency, this procedure will be repeated 500 times using independent random stratified splits. For each iteration, agreement between the two bias estimates will be quantified using a two-way random-effects absolute agreement $ICC_{(2,1)}$. ICC values will be adjusted using the Spearman-Brown correction to estimate the reliability of the full-length task. ^{47,48} For the comparison of internal consistency across tasks, reliability differences will be quantified as ΔICC using the same bootstrap procedure described for H1. At each bootstrap iteration, participants will be sampled with replacement and all observations associated with the selected participants will be retained. Within each bootstrap sample, the split-half	Sensitivity will be determined primarily from the precision of the estimated reliability indices and reliability differences. For H1, H3, and H4, directional hypotheses will be considered supported when the 95% bootstrap confidence interval for the relevant ΔICC is entirely above zero. If the confidence interval includes zero, the hypothesis will not be considered supported.	<p>The primary internal-consistency estimate will be the mean Spearman-Brown-corrected reliability estimate across the 500 splits.</p> <p>H4 will be supported when the entire 95% bootstrap CI for the split-half reliability difference is above zero.</p> <p>If the 95% bootstrap CI includes zero, evidence for a between-task difference in internal consistency will be interpreted as inconclusive.</p> <p>If the entire 95% bootstrap CI is below zero, this will be interpreted as evidence against the hypothesised internal-consistency advantage of the corresponding task.</p> <p>Split-half reliability values $\geq .80$ will be interpreted as adequate for basic research, whereas lower values will be interpreted as limited internal consistency.</p>

Question	Hypotheses	Sampling plan	Analysis plan	Rationale for deciding the sensitivity of the test for confirming or disconfirming the hypothesis	Interpretation given different outcomes
			procedure will be repeated using 100 random stratified splits.		
What are the measurement precision and systematic session effects of the scores?	No confirmatory hypothesis.		<p>Measurement precision will be quantified using the standard error of measurement (SEM), computed from the absolute-agreement ICC and the pooled standard deviation: $SEM = SD_{pooled} \times \sqrt{1 - ICC}$.</p> <p>Minimal detectable change at the 95% confidence level will be computed as $MDC95 = 1.96 \times \sqrt{2} \times SEM$.</p> <p>Systematic session effects will be examined using paired-sample t-tests comparing Time 1 and Time 2 scores. Mean differences with 95% CIs and Cohen's dz will be reported. P-values will be adjusted using Holm-Bonferroni correction.</p>		<p>Smaller SEM and MDC95 values will indicate better individual-level precision.</p> <p>A significant or meaningful Time 1-Time 2 mean difference will be interpreted as evidence of systematic session effects.</p> <p>High consistency ICC with lower agreement ICC and a systematic mean shift will be interpreted as rank-order stability with limited absolute reproducibility.</p> <p>Low consistency and low agreement ICCs will be interpreted as poor reproducibility driven by within-person variability and/or measurement error.</p> <p>High consistency and agreement ICCs with negligible mean differences will support both rank-order stability and numerical reproducibility.</p>
Are reliability estimates robust to covariate-adjustment models?	No confirmatory hypothesis.		Sensitivity analyses will include covariate-adjusted mixed-effects models, with continuous covariates standardised before analysis. Covariates include age, height, weight, time elapsed, task order and total physical activity over the previous 24 hours.		<p>If conclusions are similar across primary and sensitivity analyses, the reliability findings will be considered robust.</p> <p>If conclusions differ, the discrepancy will be reported transparently and interpreted as evidence that reliability are influenced by other factors or preprocessing choices.</p>

Note. H = hypothesis; ICC = intraclass correlation coefficient; ΔICC = difference between reliability coefficients; SEM = standard error of measurement; MDC95 = Minimal detectable change at the 95% confidence level; CI = confidence intervals.; SD = standard deviation.